

RAISING THE MORALE OF YOUNG PEOPLE TO INCREASE THEIR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY AND ACHIEVEMENTS IN THE FIELD OF SCIENCE.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569185>

Axmadova Ra'no Raximjon Qizi
Hamidjonova Ozoda Hasan qizi

The fourt course of students at the National University of Uzbekistan

Annotation: *The concept of innovative activity is closely related to such concepts as innovation, innovation process. It is therefore impossible to understand the content of innovative activity without elaborating on the content of these concepts. Innovation is an important part of practice and theory, a system of action of social actors aimed at improving the quality of the socio-cultural object. Innovations are relevant, important, new approaches formed in one system. They are born on the basis of initiatives and innovations, are promising for the development of educational content, as well as have a positive impact on the development of the education system as a whole. Innovation is the end result of a technology, form, or method in a particular field of activity or production, a new approach to solving a problem, or the application of a new technological process that is known to lead to greater success than ever before.*

Key Words: *Innovations, Technology, Internal, External, Mechanism, Cooperation, Teachers creativity, Pedagogical process.*

Depending on the direction of activity (pedagogical process, management). According to the description of the changes (radical, modified, combined). Depending on the scale of changes (local, modular, systemic) Depending on the source of origin (internal or external for this community).

The goal of innovation is to get the most out of the money or effort spent. Unlike many other spontaneous innovations, innovation is a mechanism of controlled and controlled change. Innovation is carried out within the framework of existing theory, limited in scope and time, methods are updated, and the result improves the previous system. Innovation will be systematic, integrated and sustainable, will design a new system of activities in a particular practice, will completely update the positions of the subjects of practice. At the same time, new areas of activity will be opened, new technologies will be created, new qualitative results of activities will be achieved, and as a result, the practice itself will be updated. The implementation of innovation is carried out in innovative processes. The innovation process is the process of preparing for and implementing innovative change. The author also notes that innovative changes in the educational process, the introduction of any innovations in the education system

is carried out directly through the renewal and transformation of the teaching profession. There is an opportunity to define the concept of innovative activity through the analysis of innovations in the education system, their implementation, management of innovation processes. Innovative activity is a driving force, motivating and developing the pedagogical team. "Innovative activity is an activity aimed at solving complex problems that arise as a result of the mismatch of traditional norms with new social requirements, or the collision of a newly formed norm of practice with the existing norm," - said VISlobadchikov. . Innovative activity is an important part of practice and theory, a system of action of social actors aimed at improving the quality of the socio-cultural object, which is based not only on the ability to solve certain problems, but also on motivational training to solve problems in any situation. to have. The central issue of innovative activity of the teacher is the effective organization of the educational process. Innovative activity is a continuous work on the basis of innovations, which is formed and improved over a long period of time. Based on the views of pedagogical scientists who have studied the characteristics of innovative activity of the teacher, the following can be considered the main features of innovative activity: striving to master the philosophy of creative activity; mastering pedagogical research methods; ability to create authoring concepts; be able to plan and carry out experimental work; be able to apply the experience of other researchers and teachers; cooperation with colleagues; be able to exchange ideas and provide methodological assistance; prevention and elimination of conflicts; search for innovations and adapt them to their conditions.

The approach to the problem of preparing teachers for innovative activities has emerged as a result of understanding the growing dynamics of innovation processes in society. Its analysis includes not only the use of modern advances in science and technology, but also the process of searching for, creating, adapting, implementing and re-examining the results obtained. V. Slastenin, one of the scientists who studied the structure of innovative activity, points out that it has the following structure: □The structure of innovative activity is a creative approach, creative activity, technological and methodological preparation for innovation, innovative thinking, culture of communication. Levels of innovative activity can be: reproductive, heuristic, creative. During the period of innovative activity, innovations, innovations, literally enter the educational process. Therefore, the introduction of innovations in the education system in the pedagogical process is carried out in 4 stages: 1. Identify the problem based on the analysis. 2. Design of the planned education system. 3. Planning changes and innovations. 4. Make changes.

The purpose of preparation for innovative activities is to develop the teacher's desire for innovation, the ability to work independently, to improve the skills of teaching and extracurricular activities using new pedagogical technologies, interactive methods. Use of innovative technologies in education. The four main areas of educational technology are: Person-centered learning; Teaching through computer

games; Development of interactive textbooks; Promoting learning through video games;

The modern education system is all too serious today many scientists and experts are unable to meet the requirements recognized by. The key is to change that One of the ways is the modern technological development of the education system is to attract the latest software and hardware on a large scale. One such tool is human production and the other to receive a full education without being separated from daily work is a distance education system that allows.

In recent years, the country has been carrying out practical work to support scientific and innovative activities, reform the training system, pay special attention to creating the necessary conditions for talented young people to achieve significant results in prestigious national and international Olympiads, competitions and contests. Necessary conditions are being created for the realization of creative, intellectual and entrepreneurial potential of young people, the introduction of innovative ideas, projects and technologies in production, the promotion of innovative activities of talented students, young scientists and entrepreneurs, strengthening the integration of science, education and industry. Also, the development and implementation of the state program of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev on the implementation of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Active Investment and Social Development" his order to ensure the practice also opened the door to enormous opportunities for our youth.

In short, innovative activity is the creation of a new technological process or a new improved product using scientific research, development, experiments or other scientific and technical achievements, the pragmatic feature of which is that in the field of ideas. and not in the field of action of a particular subject, but only when the experience of carrying out this activity is universal in people's lives. The essence of innovative activity is the formation of new technology in practice, the result of which is the activity aimed at transforming the invention into a project, the project into technology. In innovative activity, scientific ideas are not born of the logic of academic science, but arise from the reflection of the developing practice as a result of the support of modifications of the development process.